

CURRENT STATE OF THE INTERNATIONAL INVESTMENT MARKET AND ITS OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract. Today, the international investment market is a vast and dynamic landscape that includes a wide variety of investment opportunities and risks. In this article, the cross-border flow of investments and the international investment market are becoming an important element of the global economy with increasing globalization.

Key words. Investment, globalization, investment market, transformation, capital market.

The international investment market is a vast and dynamic landscape that includes a wide variety of investment opportunities and risks. With increasing globalization, cross-border investment flows have witnessed unprecedented growth and the international investment market has become an important element of the global economy. Understanding these market dynamics is critical for investors, policymakers and stakeholders to navigate the various trends, opportunities and challenges it presents. Therefore, this thesis aims to analyze the dynamics of the international investment market and provide insight into various investment trends and opportunities. An overview of the international investment market, including its various components such as stocks, bonds, currencies, and commodities, is provided. It also examines the role of institutional investors such as pension funds, sovereign wealth funds and hedge funds in shaping market dynamics. In addition, it assesses the impact of globalization, technology and regulations on the market. Analyzes current trends in the international investment market, such as the growth of passive investing, the shift to sustainable investing, and the growth of emerging markets. It also

examines the impact of geopolitical events such as Brexit and the US-China trade war on the market. Explores the various investment opportunities available in the international investment market, such as investing in emerging markets, alternative investments, and private equity. It also assesses the potential risks associated with these opportunities. [1]

Issues affecting the international investment market such as currency risks, political instability and global economic downturns have been identified. It also explores how investors, policy makers and stakeholders can mitigate these risks. [2]

In recent years, a number of important changes have taken place in the financial market of Uzbekistan, in particular, in accordance with the development strategy of New Uzbekistan in 2022-2026, increasing financial resources in the economy from 200 million US dollars to 7 billion dollars by introducing stock market circulation and completing transformation processes in commercial banks with a state share. , by the end of 2026, it is planned to increase the share of the private sector in the assets of the banking system to 60%. It is envisaged to accelerate the transformation of commercial banks, abandon subsidized lending, and actively transform commercial banks with state shares into modern institutions by increasing their role as financial intermediaries. [3]

He noted that great work is being done in Uzbekistan to develop the capital market, which is of great importance for banks. Today, it is very important that all necessary conditions are being created for foreign investors to enter the market in Uzbekistan.

Also, the priorities of further development of the country, prospects for the development of regional and world trade relations, mechanisms for attracting investments, liberalization of trade and increasing the competitiveness of the national economy, industrialization of the republic and the direction of the industry to the production of high value-added products. actions, measures to transform local energy and transition to alternative energy sources, to strengthen the interdependence of the countries of the region in terms of transport and to increase their transit potential.

The Tashkent International Investment Forum has come to an end, within which a package of specific agreements and investment deals worth 7.8 billion dollars was signed. According to the Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade, preliminary agreements have been reached on the implementation of projects worth 3.5 billion dollars.

The international investment market is a complex and dynamic landscape that offers a variety of investment opportunities and risks. Understanding market dynamics is essential for investors, policymakers and stakeholders to navigate current trends, seize opportunities and mitigate risks. Therefore, this thesis aims to analyze various elements of the international investment market, such as investment trends, investment opportunities and problems. It is hoped that this thesis will provide valuable insights into the international investment market and assist stakeholders in making investment decisions.

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